

**IDENTIFICATION OF FOUR – JOINTED BOX 1
AS A POTENTIAL ONCOGENE IN
NASOPHARYNGEAL CARCINOMA**

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**FACULTY OF SCIENCE
UNIVERSITY OF MALAYA
KUALA LUMPUR**

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ABSTRACT

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is a highly metastatic cancer that is endemic in South East Asia and Southern China. Despite the gravity of the disease, the current knowledge on its molecular pathogenesis is still inadequate to improve the disease management. The present study seeks to understand the molecular mechanism of NPC, with an aim to identify potential therapeutic targets or biomarkers. From a previous expression microarray study, Four – Jointed Box 1 (FJX1) gene was found to be upregulated in NPC compared to non-cancerous controls with negligible expression in 5 vital normal human organs. Human FJX1 is a *Drosophila* orthologue of *four-jointed (fj)* gene which codes for a Golgi-resident kinase that phosphorylates specific cadherin domains and functions downstream of the Notch and Hippo signaling pathways. The overexpression of FJX1 in primary NPC tissues was confirmed at both mRNA and protein levels, while its low expression was validated in 16 normal human organs. Both overexpression and knockdown experiments showed that FJX1 increased the aggressiveness of NPC cells by promoting cell proliferation, invasion and anchorage-independent growth. Concomitant change of Cyclins D1 and E1 levels were observed with FJX1 level, suggesting FJX1 enhances cell proliferation through cell cycle regulation. The results of the present study demonstrate for the first time the overexpression of FJX1 in NPC as a putative oncogene, and it represents an attractive therapeutic target for NPC.

ABSTRAK

Karsinoma nasofaring (KNF), endemik di Asia Tenggara dan Selatan China, merupakan sejenis kanser yang sangat mudah bermetastasis. Walaupun penyakit ini membawa kesan yang teruk kepada penghidapnya, pengetahuan mengenai pertumbuhan penyakit ini di peringkat molekul masih lagi tidak mencukupi untuk memperbaiki cara pengurusan penyakit tersebut. Kajian ini bertujuan untuk memahami mekanisma molekular KNF, dengan tujuan untuk mengenal pasti gen – gen yang boleh dijadikan sebagai bakal gen sasaran dalam rawatan atau sebagai gen penanda. Dengan berpandukan kajian mikroatur pengekspresan yang terdahulu, ekspresi gen Four-Jointed Box 1 (FJX1) telah dikenal pasti berada di tahap yang tinggi di KNF berbanding kumpulan kawalan bukan kanser. Ekspresi FJX1 di 5 organ manusia penting yang normal pula berada pada tahap yang sangat rendah. Gen manusia FJX1 adalah ortolog kepada gen *Drosophila* bergelar *four-jointed (fj)*, yang mana protinnya merupakan kinase di Golgi yang memfosforilasi domain-domain cadherin tertentu. *Fj* juga berfungsi di bawah kawalan tapak jalan Notch dan Hippo. Peningkatan FJX1 di KNF telah dipastikan pada kedua-dua tahap, baik di tahap mRNA mahupun di tahap protin. Ekspresinya juga telah disahkan rendah di 16 organ manusia normal. Eksperimen–eksperimen *in vitro* telah menunjukkan bahawa FJX1 meningkatkan sifat agresif sel-sel KNF dengan menggalakkan pertubuhan, penyerbuan, dan pertumbuhan tanpa lekap sel-sel tersebut. Perubahan sekali gus tahap Cyclin D1 dan Cyclin E1 bersama-sama tahap FJX1 juga didapati — ini menunjukkan bahawa FJX1 menggalakkan pertumbuhan melalui proses kitaran sel. Hasil kajian ini membuktikan buat julung kalinya peningkatan tahap FJX1 di KNF, dan sebagai sebagai bakal gen penyebab kanser, gen ini juga merupakan sasaran bagi rawatan yang berpotensi bagi KNF.

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Nothing is permanent in this wicked world – not even our troubles.

Charlie Chaplin.

Actor, director, screenwriter (1889 – 1977)

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LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

°C	degrees Celcius
μg	microgram
μl	microliter
μM	micromolar
bp	base pair
<i>g</i>	force of gravity
g	gram
hr	hour
kb	kilobase pair
kDa	kiloDalton
M	molar
mg	milligram
min	minute (time)
ml	milliliter
mM	millimolar
mm ²	milimeter square
ng	nanogram
rpm	revolution per minute
sec	second (time)
U	enzyme unit
v/v	volume per volume

ADPRT	poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase 1
BART	<i>Bam</i> HIA rightward transcripts
BCL-2	B-cell leukemia/lymphoma 2
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BSA	bovine serum albumin
CapG	capping protein (actin filament), gelsolin-like
CARIF	Cancer Research Initiatives Foundation
CCND1	cyclin D1
CCNE1	cyclin E1
CD200	cluster of differentiation 200
CD44	cluster of differentiation 44
CDK2	cyclin dependent kinase 2
CDK4	cyclin dependent kinase 4
CDKN1B	cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1B
CDKN2A-CDKN2B	cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A-cyclin-dependent kinase 4 inhibitor B
cDNA	complementary DNA
CGH	comparative genomic hybridization
CHEK1	CHK1 checkpoint homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
CK10	keratin 10
CK5	keratin 5
CLCA2	chloride channel accessory 2

CLDN1	claudin 1
CLIC1	chloride intracellular channel 1
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
CT	cycle threshold
DAB	diamino benzidine
DMSO	dimethyl sulfoxide
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
DNA-PKC	deoxyribonucleic acid-protein kinase catalytic polypeptide
dNTP	deoxynucleotide triphosphate
DPX	<i>P</i> -xylylene- <i>A,A'</i> -bispyridinium dibromide
Ds	dachsous
DTT	dithiothreitol
EBER1	Epstein-Barr virus encoded-RNA 1
EBER2	Epstein-Barr virus encoded-RNA 2
EBNA1	Epstein-Barr nuclear antigen
EBV	Epstein-Barr virus
EDTA	ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EGF	epidermal growth factor
EGFR	epidermal growth factor receptor
EHS	Engelbreth-Holm-Swarm
EM	extracellular matrix
EMT	epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition
ERCC1	excision repair cross-complementing rodent repair deficiency, complementation group 1

Erk	mitogen-activated protein kinase 1
ESI-Q-TOF MS	electrospray ionization-quadrupole time-of-flight MS
EST	expressed sequence tag
EZH2	enhancer of zeste homolog 2 (Drosophila)
FACS	fluorescent activated cell sorter
Fat4	FAT tumor suppressor homolog 4 (Drosophila)
FBS	fetal bovine serum
FFPE	formalin-fixed paraffin embedded
FGFR3	fibroblast growth factor receptor 3
Fj	four-jointed
FJX1	four-jointed box 1
Ft	fat
FZD6	frizzled family receptor 6
FZD7	frizzled family receptor 7
GABBR1	gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) B receptor, 1
GAPDH	glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
GSK-3beta	glycogen synthase kinase 3 beta
HCl	hydrochloric acid
HDAC1	histone deacetylase 1
HLA	Human Leukocyte Antigen
HMGB1	high-mobility group box 1
HOGG1	8-oxoguanine DNA glycosylase
IMRT	intensity-modulated radiotherapy
IPTG	isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside

ITGA9	integrin alpha-9
JAK/STAT	janus kinase / signal transducer and activator of transcription
KSFM	keratinocyte serum-free medium
LATS2	large tumor suppressor, homolog 2 (Drosophila)
LB	Laura-Bertani
LMP2A	latent membrane protein 2A
LMP2B	latent membrane protein 2B
MDS1-EVI1	ecotropic viral integration site 1
Mek	mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 1
MgCl ₂	magnesium chloride
MHC	Major Histocompatibility Complex
miRNA	micro RNA
mRNA	messenger RNA
MS	mass spectrometry
MTC	Multiple Tissue cDNA
Myc	myelocytomatosis viral oncogene homolog (avian)
Na ₃ VO ₄	Sodium orthovanadate
NaCl	Sodium chloride
NaOH	Sodium hydroxide
NP-40	nonyl phenoxyethoxyethanol
NPC	nasopharyngeal carcinoma
P53	protein 53
PAGE	polyacrylamide gel
PBL	peripheral blood leukocyte

PBS	phosphate buffer saline
PBST	phosphate buffer saline Tween-20
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
pEGFR	phosphorylated EGFR
pERK	phosphorylated ERK
PRKDC	protein kinase, DNA-activated, catalytic polypeptide
qPCR	quantitative real-time PCR
RAD23A	UV excision repair protein RAD23 homolog A
RAD23B	UV excision repair protein RAD23 homolog B
Raf	v-raf murine leukemia viral oncogene homolog
RALA	v-ral simian leukemia viral oncogene homolog A (ras related)
Ras	RAS p21 protein activator (GTPase activating protein) 1
RASSF1A	ras association domain-containing protein 1A
RASSF2	ras association domain-containing protein 2
RIPA	radioimmuno precipitation assay
RKIP	phosphatidylethanolamine binding protein 1
RNA	ribonucleic acid
RNAi	RNA interference
RPMI	Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium
RQ	relative quantification
S100A9	S100 calcium binding protein A9
SCCA1	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade B (ovalbumin), member 4
SDS	sodium dodecyl sulphate

SELDI-TOF MS	surface-enhanced laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry
semi-qPCR	semi-quantitative PCR
siRNA	small interfering RNA
STR	single tandem repeat
TNFRSF19	tumor necrosis factor receptor superfamily, member 19
Tris	tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane
USA	the United States of America
UTR	untranslated region
UV	ultra violet
VEGF	vascular endothelial growth factor
WHO	World Health Organization
WIF-1	wnt inhibitory factor 1
WNT5A	wingless-type MMTV integration site family, member 5A
X-Gal	bromo-chloro-indolyl-galactopyranoside
XPC	xeroderma pigmentosum, complementation group C
XPD	excision repair cross-complementing rodent repair deficiency, complementation group 2
XRCC1	X-ray repair complementing defective repair in Chinese hamster cells 1
YAP	yes-associated protein 1
ZO-1	tight junction protein 1 (zona occludens 1)

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL INTRODUCTION ON CANCER

Cancer is a diverse group of diseases that share abnormal cell proliferation as a leitmotif. Essentially, failure of normal cells to regulate their growth causes them to be transformed and become cancerous. In 2000, Hanahan and Weinberg proposed six ‘cancer hallmarks’ – defined as the biological capabilities that are acquired by the transformed cells. The original cancer hallmarks were initially defined as sustaining cell proliferation, evading growth suppressors, activating invasion and metastasis, enabling replicative immortality, inducing angiogenesis, and resisting cell death (Hanahan & Weinberg, 2000). In addition, two emerging hallmarks have been recently proposed: reprogramming of cellular metabolism, and resistance to antagonisms from the immune systems. Underneath these hallmarks are two factors that precipitate their acquisition by the cells: the instability of the genome, as well as the inflammatory state of the neoplastic lesions (Hanahan & Weinberg, 2011).

Microarray has been widely used to identify genes that are differentially expressed between normal and cancerous cells. However, a lot of dysregulated genes are still of uncertain significance to the transformation process. It is necessary to examine the impact of altering the level of a gene on the cancer hallmark traits in order to implicate it as a true ‘driver’ of oncogenesis, instead of a mere ‘passenger’ event. Ultimately, for a gene that is overexpressed in cancer, the impairment of the hallmark capabilities as a result of the inhibition of the gene function could be the basis of therapeutic development. In addition, the identification of a gene that does not directly correlate with the hallmark traits but correlate instead with a disease parameter would qualify the gene to be developed as a biomarker. The results of these studies would advance the still rudimentary understanding of the molecular underpinnings of cancer, in the hope that this knowledge would translate to better disease management in the clinic.

1.2 NASOPHARYNGEAL CARCINOMA

1.2.1 Background

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is a type of cancer that arises from the epithelial lining of the nasopharynx (hence nasopharyngeal carcinoma), the uppermost area of the throat. It usually arises from the lateral nasopharyngeal recess of the Rosenmüller fossa. NPC is distinct from other types of head and neck cancer on the grounds of incidence, risk factors, clinical behavior, as well as association with the Epstein - Barr virus (EBV).

1.2.2 Histopathology

Histopathological classification of NPC, as proposed by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 1978, categorizes the disease into three types based on the degree of the tumor cell differentiation. Type I consists of well differentiated keratinizing squamous carcinoma cells, with occurrence of intercellular bridges and general cell keratinization. Types II and III consists of non-keratinizing cells, with Type II formed by moderately-differentiated cells, while Type III being made up of undifferentiated cells.

1.2.3 Epidemiology

NPC is extremely rare in most countries, with incidence less than 1 case in 100,000 people. Cases that do occur in Western Europe or in the United States are mainly of the differentiated Type I diseases (Brugere et al., 1978; Chow et al., 1993; Vaughan et al., 1996). However, outstandingly high incidence among people of Southern Chinese descendants are observed both in their homeland and the place where they migrate to; incidence in Southern Chinese cities Guangzhou and Zhongshan are 22 and 27 respectively, while in Hong Kong is

18, and Singapore is 11 per 100,000 population (Curado et al., 2007). Moderately high incidence of around 4 cases in 100,000 population meanwhile occurs among the North Africans, the Inuits in Greenland, as well as among the Filipinos. In all affected populations the ratio of male to female is consistently about 3 to 1.

In our local context, NPC is the fifth most common cancer overall and the third most common among Peninsular Malaysia males (Figure 1A). In addition, among Peninsular men of the productive age bracket from 15 to 49 years, NPC is the most frequent cancer (Figure 1B) (Omar et al., 2006). Moreover, its incidence among the indigenous Bidayuh people of Sarawak is the highest known in the world (Devi et al., 2004).

Figure 1.1 | NPC incidence in Peninsular Malaysia, 2006. (A) NPC is the third most frequent cancer among Peninsular Malaysia males, among which in 15-49 years old age bracket the cancer is the most frequent. Image adapted from the National Cancer Registry 2006 (Omar et al., 2006).

1.2.4 Etiological Factors

1.2.4.1 Genetic

The most well-studied genetic susceptibility factor of NPC is the HLA locus. HLA genes encode for cell-surface proteins that present peptides from the inside of a cell, including those of foreign (e.g viral or bacterial) origin. The presentation of these peptides is necessary for correct immune function. HLA involvement in NPC was initially thought to be as a result of its inability to present EBV epitopes correctly, but there is no evident difference between the EBV peptide binding by the different HLA that are associated with disease risk (Li et al., 2009). The association of HLA with an increased risk in NPC has been documented as early as in the 1970s among the Chinese (Simons et al., 1974). Among the population HLA alleles A2, B14 and B46 confer increased risk while A11, B13 and B22 confer negative risk for the disease (Goldsmith et al., 2002). However, even though some alleles carry an increased risk for NPC in one population, the same alleles could carry a decreased risk for the disease in another (Boussen et al., 2005).

In addition, other studies have also pointed to the presence of different genetic elements other than HLA genes, close to the MHC region in chromosome 6 as a genetic susceptibility factor (Ooi et al., 1997). Genome wide association studies meanwhile have further implicated novel susceptibility loci that code for ITGA9, GABBR1, TNRSF19, MDS1-EVI1 and CDKN2A-CDKN2B (Ng et al., 2009; Tse et al., 2009; Bei et al., 2010).

1.2.4.2 Diet

The importance of diet as an etiological factor was first recognized with the finding that consumption of salted fish that contains nitrosamines carries a strong predisposition for the disease development among the Southern Chinese (Fong & Walsh, 1971; Zou et al.,

1992). Specifically, the consumption of the salted fish during early childhood and at high regularity correlates with an increased risk of developing NPC (Armstrong et al., 1983; Yu et al., 1983; Yu & Henderson 1987; Guo et al., 2009). Nitrosamine-containing food remains a predisposing risk even in non-endemic population such as in the United States, where the study subjects are Caucasian and African American (Farrow et al., 1998). In addition, the expression levels of nitrosamine metabolism pathway components are also down-regulated in the cancerous tissue as reported in a global gene expression study (Dodd et al., 2006). Further support has come from the experimental evidence in animals that showed the rodents develop carcinomas of nasal cavities when fed with salted fish (Huang et al., 1978; Yu et al., 1989). A derivative of nitrosamines, *N,N'*-dinitrosopiperzine could reproducibly induce NPC in rats with no cancer in other organs was observed (Pan et al., 1978). Apart from nitrosamine, consumption of food that contains butyric acid, such as rancid butter, sheep fat and *quaddid* (preserved meat) was also associated with an increased NPC incidence among the North Africans (Feng et al., 2007) by activating the lytic cycle of EBV (Bauer, 1983).

1.2.4.3 Epstein - Barr Virus

Epstein - Barr virus is a human γ -herpesvirus with a double-stranded linear DNA genome of about 170kbp. It latently infects 90% of world human population. EBV presence is detectable as early as in high grade pre-invasive (severe dysplasia and carcinoma *in situ*) nasopharyngeal tissue. The clonal nature of the viral genome in the NPC cells also supports the postulate that the viral infection occurs very early during the disease progression (Pathmanathan et al., 1995).

Virtually all undifferentiated NPC cases (Types II and III) are associated with EBV. The latent form of the virus always exists in the cancerous cells but were absent in the

surrounding normal tissues. EBV infection in NPC cells falls under latency Type II, where all cells express viral genes EBNA1, EBER1, EBER2, LMP2A and LMP2B, while LMP1 is present in most NPC tumor cells.

1.2.5 Clinical Presentation

Over 80% of the patients come at late stage because of the non-specific nature of the nasal and aural symptoms, as well as the difficulty for clinical assessment of the nasopharynx (Pua et al., 2008). The presenting clinical symptoms can be divided according to the anatomical sites that are invaded and affected as the tumor develops: 1) nasopharyngeal tumor mass leading to epistaxis (nosebleed), nasal obstruction and nasal discharge; 2) Eustachian tube malfunction leading to tinnitus (ringing in the ear) and deafness; 3) skull-base erosion and cranial nerve palsy leading to headache, diplopia (double vision) and numbness; and 4) metastases to lymph nodes leading to lymphadenopathy (enlarged lymph nodes), characterized by gross neck mass (Wei & Sham, 2005). Patients come to the clinic with complaints of cervical lymphadenopathy as the most common symptom, followed by nasal, aural and other ophthalmic-neurologic symptoms (Chan et al., 2002; Pua et al., 2008).

1.2.6 Treatment

Stage I and IIa diseases are most often treated with radiotherapy. Whenever possible, 3D conformal therapy or even Intensity-Modulated Radiation Therapy (IMRT) is preferred over standard 2D conventional radiotherapy (Chao et al., 2000). As earlier stage tumors are highly radiosensitive, overall survival rate after radiotherapy as high as 85% for Stages I and II could be achieved. However, the overall survival rate falls to 55% for Stages III and IV due to local failure and distant metastasis (Teo et al., 1996). Locoregionally advanced (Stages IIb

to IV) diseases are treated with a combination of chemotherapy and radiotherapy (Al-Sarraf et al., 1998; Lin et al., 2003). Adjuvant chemotherapy usually involves cisplatin and 5-fluorouracil while concurrent chemotherapy involves cisplatin alone. Currently, concurrent chemoradiotherapy seems to be more efficacious (Wei & Sham, 2005). Although long-term diseases-free survivors for patients with metastases have been reported, treatment of metastatic nasopharyngeal carcinoma is essentially palliative (Fandi et al., 2000).

1.3 CURRENT MOLECULAR UNDERSTANDING OF NPC

1.3.1 Cytogenetic Studies

During NPC development the nasopharyngeal epithelial cells suffers from progressive and incremental genomic change, suggesting that the genetic change is a progressive multi-step event (Chen et al., 1999), rather than a single catastrophic chromotripsis event (Stephens et al., 2011). 3p and 9p21 chromosomal deletions are probably the earliest recognizable events in NPC. These lesions occur in normal adult epithelium in high risk population, leading to specific inactivation of RASSF1A (at 3p) and p16 (at 9p) tumor suppressors (Chan et al., 2000; Chan et al., 2002; Shao et al., 2002), even though these tumor suppressors can also be inactivated via methylation (Lo et al., 2001). These events might incline nasopharyngeal cells to latent EBV infection (Chan et al., 2004). Gain in chromosome 12 could be another important early event, and may represent a different subclass of NPC from those that carry 3p loss (Shih-Hsin Wu, 2006).

Some patterns of genomic lesion are consistent in both early and late cases, with a trend for these lesions to occur at a higher frequency in advanced cases (Li et al., 2006). Gain of 3p, 8q, 12p, 12q, and loss of 14p and 14q commonly seen across the stages suggests that these lesions might be essential lesions for the disease progression, or that these are

fundamental lesions that actually occur during early oncogenesis (Li et al., 2006). Advanced NPC cases exhibit a strong association with gain of 1q, 8q, 18q and loss of 9q, 11q, 16q (Chien et al., 2001; Fang et al., 2001; Shao et al., 2002; Li et al., 2006). Gain at 1q is seen at much higher frequency in Mediterranean cases than in Asian cases (Rodriguez et al., 2005). Even though some lesions are frequently observed in cases regardless of stages, none of them are seen in more than 30% of all cases (Li et al., 2006).

For recurrent tumors, 11q13 amplification which can already be observed in primary tumors becomes more frequent with no new identifiable lesions, suggesting that the tumor could utilize other mechanisms to generate the genetic diversity required for survival (Chen et al., 1999). For neck lymph node metastases, more extensive alterations in the form gains of 8p and 8q as well as loss of 9p, 16p, 7q, 20q, 21p, 21q, 22q are detected, implying that the primary tumor cells had to undergo more genomic changes for the metastases to become successful (Yan et al., 2005).

From the information on genomic alterations of NPC tumors, it has been postulated that the disease pathogenesis possibly does not follow a simplistic and rigid linear model. A different approach involving distance-based and branching-tree methods to construct more general tree-like models have been proposed as an alternative: NPC can be classified into two groups, one marked by gains at 12p12 and 8q22, and the other group (3p-deficient NPC) by gain in 1q22-32 plus loss in 3p26, 11q22, 14q24 (Huang et al., 2004). Another study further proposed a refined version of this model, by suggesting that there are at least two subclasses of 3p-deficient derived NPC, one marked by gain in 1q plus loss of 9p and 13q, while the other marked by loss of 14q, 16q, 9q, and 1p (Shih-Hsin Wu, 2006).

1.3.2 Molecular Alterations

1.3.2.1 Dysregulation of the Signaling Pathways

1.3.2.1.1 The Wnt Pathway

The Wnt signaling pathway is involved in a number of normal physiological processes including organ morphogenesis, maintenance of adult stem cell (Sugimura & Li, 2010), determination of cell polarity (Wallingford & Mitchell, 2011), and nervous system wiring (Salinas & Zou, 2008). Aberrant expression of Wnt pathway components has been repeatedly documented in NPC cases of different origins from global gene expression studies, suggesting that Wnt pathway dysregulation is critical for NPC progression regardless of ethnic origin (Shi et al., 2006; Sriuranpong et al., 2004; Zeng et al., 2007).

At the upstream level of the pathway and at the extracellular of the cell, the increased WNT5A ligand (Zeng et al., 2007) and the downregulation of an antagonist of Wnt proteins WIF-1 (Chan et al., 2007; Fendri et al., 2010) have been shown in NPC. Furthermore, Fzd7, a receptor of the Wnt proteins, has also been shown to be upregulated (Zeng et al., 2007). Beta-catenin is a downstream molecule of Wnt pathway that is translocated from the membrane to the nucleus and act as transcriptional coactivator on pathway activation. The protein was observed to be localized at the membrane of non-malignant nasopharyngeal tissues (Galera-Ruiz et al., 2011), but loses its membrane localization with corresponding increase in nuclear localization in NPC (Wang et al., 2009). The increase of beta-catenin in the tumor cells also correlates with higher tumor staging (Galera-Ruiz et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2009). In addition, a regulator of beta-catenin, GSK-3beta has been shown to be phosphorylated in NPC, which would result in its ability to antagonize beta-catenin transcriptional activation function (Morrison et al., 2004). Furthermore, oncogenic mutation

in beta-catenin, which increases its stability in other cancers, is a rare event in NPC (Li et al., 2004).

1.3.2.1.2 The EGFR Pathway

Various components of the EGFR signaling transduction pathway have been studied in NPC. The EGFR gene is amplified (Hui et al., 2002) and overexpressed in NPC (Fang et al., 2007). The expression of EGFR (Wang et al., 2006; Yang et al., 2009; Cao et al., 2011) and its active form pEGFR (Yuan et al., 2008) has been shown to be associated with poor prognosis. The expression of EGFR also correlates with disease staging (Chua et al., 2004; Yuan et al., 2008) and it persists in lymph node metastases (Huang et al., 2009).

Ras, Raf, and Erk belong to the same signaling cascade that could be affected by the signal from activated EGFR. RASSF2, a negative regulator of Ras is downregulated and its low expression correlates with lymph node metastasis (Zhang et al., 2007). Meanwhile, Raf kinase inhibitor protein (RKIP), a negative regulator of Raf, is differentially phosphorylated in NPC, and its downregulation was significantly correlated with advanced clinical stage, lymph node metastasis and radioresistance (Chen et al., 2008; Chen et al., 2009; Ruan et al., 2010).

However, despite the information pointing to the hyperactivation of the EGFR signaling pathway in NPC, a clinical trial using Gefitinib, a small molecule inhibitor of wild type EGFR shows that the drug has very limited activity in recurrent NPC cases (Ma et al., 2008), despite the fact that EGFR protein in NPC bears no mutation (Naji et al., 2010). Treatment with Sorafenib, a Raf/Erk inhibitor had only modest anticancer activity in NPC, despite the tumor showing a decrease in activate ERK after the drug treatment (Elser et al., 2007). The results from these two clinical trials suggest that, different from cancers for which

Gefitinib and Sorafenib have been successful, the dysregulation of the EGFR pathway and its components may confer a fundamentally different effect to NPC pathogenesis that is yet to be understood.

1.3.2.2 Overexpression of the DNA Repair Pathway Components

As high as about 93% genes that are annotated within the DNA repair pathways are overexpressed in NPC as reported in a global gene expression study (Dodd et al., 2006). Overexpression of a number of genes, including HMGB1, DNA-PKCs, ERCC1 and Topoisomerase II α have been shown to correlate with disease staging, poor survival and poor prognosis (Xiang et al., 2004; Ding et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2010). In contrast, downregulation of several components of the DNA repair pathway, including ATM (Bose et al., 2009), ADPRT and HOGG1 (Liu et al., 2008) have also been observed.

A peculiar feature of NPC is the overexpression of intact P53, in contrast to the general observation that P53 mutation or downregulation are ubiquitous in most human cancers. The overexpression (Hsu et al., 2002; Agaoglu et al., 2004; Chen et al., 2004; Hoe et al., 2009) and the wild type nature (Spruck et al., 1992; Sun et al., 1992; Sheu et al., 2004; Hoe et al., 2009) of the protein has been well documented in NPC cases of various origins. Its expression is also associated with a better response to chemotherapy and better survival (Hsu et al., 2002). The reason for its overexpression in NPC is still unclear. Even more intriguing is that p53 overexpression might occur before EBV infection of the nasopharyngeal dysplasia (Gulley et al., 1998).

1.3.2.3 Dysregulation of the Cell Cycle Components

The dysregulated expression of G1-S transition phase components of the cell cycle has been consistently documented in global gene expression studies of NPC (Xie et al., 2000; Sengupta et al., 2006; Sriuranpong et al., 2006; Zeng et al., 2007). Cyclin D1 is overexpressed (Xie et al., 2000; Zhang et al., 2009; Acikalin et al., 2011) and amplified in NPC (Hui et al., 2005). The expression of cyclin D1 correlates with early local recurrence and poorer prognosis (Lai et al., 2002; Zhang et al., 2009), and has been proposed as a predictor to local recurrence after radiotherapy for NPC (Hwang et al., 2002). Furthermore, polymorphism of the gene promoter was associated with inherent susceptibility to NPC (Deng et al., 2002).

p27 (encoded by the CDKN1B gene) and p16 (encoded by the CDKN2A gene) proteins control the cell cycle progression at G1 by inhibiting cyclin D1/CDK4 and cyclin E1/CDK2 complexes. These proteins are downregulated at the early stage of NPC development, possibly after the nasopharyngeal hyperplastic lesions (Fan et al., 2006). Furthermore, low expression of p27 correlates with cranial nerve encroaching (Li & Zhang, 2003) and loco-regional recurrence (Hwang et al., 2003), while loss of p16 was related to post-radiotherapy recurrence (Hwang et al., 2002; Makitie et al., 2003).

1.3.2.4 Dysregulation of Global miRNA Expression Profile

There are three reports on the dysregulation of human miRNA profile in NPC (Sengupta et al., 2008; Chen et al., 2009; Li et al., 2011). It is possible to segregate NPC cases according to clinical stages based on global profile of miRNA alone (Li et al., 2011), an exhibit not possible using expression profile of non-miRNA transcripts (Zeng et al., 2007).

Some of the dysregulated miRNA which biological roles are relatively well-characterized warrant further attention.

A number of miRNAs are downregulated in NPC and function as tumor suppressors by regulating extracellular matrix protein expression (miR-29c; (Sengupta et al., 2008), and targeting the oncogene EZH2 (miR-26a; (Alajez et al., 2010; Lu et al., 2011). On the other hand, major oncomiRs that are overexpressed in NPC include miR-17-92 cluster, miR-155 and miR-141 (Chen et al., 2009). Polycistronic miR-17-92, also known as oncomir-1, is a strongly oncogenic family of miRNAs that inhibits differentiation as well as enhances proliferation, angiogenesis and cell survival (Olive et al., 2010). Mir-155 is pleiotropically involved in differentiation, immunity, inflammation, and its expression is also increased in a variety of cancers (Faraoni et al., 2009). The overexpression of miR-141 meanwhile increases cisplatin resistance in esophageal cancer cells (Imanaka et al., 2011).

Reports investigating the EBV miRNA transcriptome in NPC have revealed a consistent pattern of viral miRNA expression in NPC (Chen et al., 2009; Cosmopoulos et al., 2009; Zhu et al., 2009; Gourzones et al., 2010). BART miRNAs that may negatively regulates EBV proteins LMP1 (Lo et al., 2007) and LMP2A (Lung et al., 2009) are expressed abundantly in NPC tumors and are released into the blood (Cosmopoulos et al., 2009; Zhu et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2010; Gourzones et al., 2010). Meanwhile, prosurvival (Li et al., 2006; Desbien et al., 2009) BHRF1 miRNAs are not expressed in NPC cells (Cosmopoulos et al., 2009; Zhu et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2010). Finally, C666.1 being the only EBV positive cell line, shows viral miRNA expression that is generally representative for NPC tumors (Cosmopoulos et al., 2009).

1.3.2.5 Proteomics Studies

Four independent proteomic studies have identified ceruloplasmin and chloride intracellular channel 1 (CLIC1) as potential serum biomarkers for NPC. These proteins are also overexpressed in the primary tumors (Doustjalali et al., 2006; Chen et al., 2008; Chang et al., 2009; Chang et al., 2010). Serum protein profiling was also shown to be able to discriminate between NPC and healthy controls (Wei et al., 2008; Huang et al., 2009) and to differentiate between tumors that predominantly invade to the cranium versus tumors that would mainly manifest by extensive cervical lymph node metastasis (Guo et al., 2005). In addition, two separate studies have shown the existence of serum autoantibodies against NPC tumor proteins (Xiao et al., 2007; Tong et al., 2008). Studies comparing primary NPC tissues against normal epithelium shows that cathepsin D and stathmin are upregulated while 14-3-3 σ , annexin I and SCCA1 are downregulated in NPC (Cheng et al., 2008; Yi et al., 2008; Xiao et al., 2010). Meanwhile, one laboratory has developed an online-accessible NPC proteome database from proteomic data generated from two-dimensional gel electrophoresis (Li et al., 2006; Li et al., 2007; Peng et al., 2009). Proteomic studies investigating differential protein expression of the stroma of NPC versus normal nasopharyngeal epithelial tissues revealed the differential protein level of CapG (Li et al., 2010), L-plastin as well as S100A9 (Li et al., 2009).

1.4 THE FOUR-JOINTED BOX ONE (FJX1) HUMAN GENE

The human FJX1 gene had no previous association with NPC. In this study, FJX1 was identified as the gene of interest as it was found to be upregulated in NPC, while expressed at limited amount in normal organs. While the exact function of FJX1 in human is unknown, subsequent information below describes current knowledge on FJX1 and its counterparts in other species. Also described is the amplification of 11p13, the region where FJX1 resides, in many human cancers.

1.4.1 Background

The human FJX1 was first identified via Expressed Sequence Tag (EST) clone isolation (Thate et al., 1995). The gene contains a single exon at chromosome 11p13 (Figure 1.2). The FJX1 protein is predicted to be a type II transmembrane glycoprotein, consisting of a short cytoplasm-facing C-terminus tail, a single transmembrane domain, followed by a predicted signal peptidase cleavage site, and a longer N-terminus region that could be facing inside of Golgi apparatus and/or the extracellular space (Figure 1.3). The protein shares 29% identity with its *Drosophila* equivalent Four-jointed (Fj) and 88% identity with mouse FJX1 (Rock et al., 2005).

Figure 1.2| Chromosomal location of human FJX1. FJX1 is located at 11p13 chromosome. Image generated from Ensembl (<http://www.ensembl.org>).

Figure 1.3| Human FJX1 protein. Human FJX1 is predicted to be a type II transmembrane glycoprotein, and shares 29% identity with *Drosophila* Fj (Villano & Katz, 1995; Rock et al., 2005), a Golgi-resident kinase which phosphorylates specific cadherins in two membrane-bound proteins Fat (Ft) and Dachshous (Ds) (Ishikawa et al., 2008). A previously documented crucial aspartic acid-asparagine-glutamine (DNE) motif for its kinase activity is conserved in human FJX1. Diagram of Fj is adapted from Villano & Katz (1995). Asterisks (*) denotes potential *N*-linked glycosylation sites. “EM” denotes the extracellular matrix space.

Figure 1.4| Protein sequence alignment of human and mouse FJX1 and *Drosophila* Fj. Red box denotes the conserved DNE motif crucial for kinase activity in Fj (Ishikawa et al., 2008). Highly hydrophobic neighboring residues are also conserved across the species (immediate left and right of the red box), suggestive of the conservation of the kinase activity.

1.4.2 Subcellular Localization

A proteomic study on proteins secreted by human ovarian cancer cell line ES2 reported that FJX1 can be found in culture medium (Faca et al., 2008). Its mouse counterpart has also been shown to be secreted into the medium (Rock et al., 2005). Addition of recombinant mouse FJX1 to the culture medium causes a decrease in dendrite extension in cultured mouse neurons - the same effect conferred by FJX1 overexpression from plasmid transfection to the cells itself (Probst et al., 2007). On the flipside, secretion of *Drosophila* Four-jointed is not crucial for its function, and its preferential localization in the Golgi is accompanied by an elevated functional activity (Strutt et al., 2004).

1.4.3 Molecular Function

The exact molecular function of human FJX1 is unknown. In *Drosophila*, Fj is a Golgi-resident kinase that phosphorylates specific cadherin domains in two gigantic transmembrane proteins Fat and Dachous (Ishikawa et al., 2008) to regulate their heterodimeric interaction (Brittle et al., 2010; Simon et al., 2010). The aspartic acid-asparagine-glutamic acid (DNE) motif that is crucial for the kinase activity is conserved in human and mouse (Figures 1.3 and 1.4), as well as in other FJX1 proteins in other animals.

Clues in other species hint that human FJX1 could be a part of several biological pathways. The Fj, the *Drosophila* Fat and its murine orthologue Fat4 have been shown to control the Hippo tumor suppressor pathway that regulates organ size by regulating proliferation and apoptosis (Bao et al., 2011). The corruption of this pathway has been increasingly recognized in many different human cancers (Zhao et al., 2010). In mouse, either the loss of Fat4 or an increase in the activity of the pathway effector YAP is accompanied by increased FJX1 expression (Happe et al., 2011; Saburi et al., 2008). In addition, both

Drosophila Fj and murine FJX1 were shown to be involved in the Notch signaling pathway (Buckles et al., 2001; Rock et al., 2005). Furthermore, Gutierrez-Avino *et al.*, has shown that Fj also mediates the function of JAK/STAT pathway, and that Fj might be a regulatory node that integrates multiple growth-controlling pathways in flies (Gutierrez-Avino et al., 2009).

Currently there is not much knowledge available on the status of the aforementioned pathways in NPC. A component of the Hippo pathway LATS2, largely known to function as tumor suppressors in other cancers, is overexpressed as a result of demethylation in NPC, and its expression is an indicator of poor prognosis (Zhang et al., 2010). Meanwhile, the Notch signaling pathway is predominantly activated in a subpopulation of NPC cells that co-express embryonic stem cell markers (Zhang et al., 2010).

1.4.4 Physiological Function

Various studies have pointed to possible involvement of FJX1 in animal development. *In situ* hybridization analyses have demonstrated specific FJX1 expression in early developing neuronal structures of chicken (Yamaguchi et al., 2006), mouse (Ashery-Padan et al., 1999) and zebrafish, where its expression is regulated by the epigenetic regulator Histone Deacetylase (HDAC1) (Harrison et al., 2011). FJX1 is also specifically expressed in neural but is absent in embryonic stem cells in mice (D'Amour & Gage, 2003). FJX1 is also important in the proper neuronal function as cultured neurons derived from FJX1 null mice were defective in forming dendrite branching, an important cellular structure for neuronal cell function, even though the knockout FJX1 mice were viable and fertile (Probst et al., 2007). Furthermore, the brain of adult mice also express very low FJX1 transcript (Ashery-Padan et al., 1999; Rock et al., 2005a; Rock et al., 2005b).

FJX1 might also be important in kidney physiology. Simultaneous loss of FJX1 and Fat4 synergistically worsens cystic defects in mouse kidneys (Saburi et al., 2008). FJX1 expression is also required for tissue regeneration in mouse kidney after injury (Happe et al., 2009). Furthermore, even though murine FJX1 is expressed in the kidneys of mouse embryo, it is no longer expressed in adult kidneys (Li et al., 2009). Together, this suggests that FJX1 might be important in the development and tissue repair of murine kidney.

Other clues hint strongly at FJX1 possible involvement in tissue proliferation and organ growth. FJX1 is expressed at the proliferation zone of the lens and the feather buds of developing chicken (Yamaguchi et al., 2006). It is also expressed during limb outgrowth in chick (Yamaguchi et al., 2006) and in mouse (Ashery-Padan et al., 1999). In addition, RNAi experiments targeting FJX1 during cricket leg regeneration resulted in slight leg shortening in the insects after leg amputation (Bando et al., 2009).

Other studies on FJX1 counterparts meanwhile point to their role in regulating planar cell polarity (the patterning of epithelial cells) in flies (Zeidler et al., 2000; Casal et al., 2002; Simon et al., 2004; Strutt et al., 2004; Segalen et al., 2009; Zhu et al., 2009) and in mouse (Saburi et al., 2008). Interestingly, in developing mouse kidney, lung and intestine, FJX1 is expressed by the epithelial cells that reside at the boundary of the mesenchymal-epithelial interaction in the organs (Rock et al., 2005a; Rock et al., 2005b). Collectively, these studies suggest that FJX1 proteins might be involved in the physiology of the nervous system and the kidneys, in proliferating cells during organ development and regeneration, as well as in planar cell polarity determination.

1.4.5 FJX1 in Neoplasia

1.4.5.1 Expression

FJX1 transcript is upregulated in ovarian tumor vasculature (Buckanovich et al., 2007; Lu et al., 2007). Buckanovich *et al.*, also further reported that FJX1 is expressed in reproductive tissues with physiological angiogenesis (e.g. corpus luteum, endometrium, placenta) at almost similar level as in ovarian-tumor derived endothelial cells, suggesting that FJX1 might have a role in the process (Buckanovich et al., 2007). In addition, in mice injected with human small cell lung cancer cells, FJX1 was found to be predominantly expressed in metastatic cells in the kidneys (Kakiuchi et al., 2003). On the contrary, FJX1 was found to be downregulated in mycosis fungoides, a form of cutaneous T-cell lymphoma, when compared to inflamed dermal tissues (Tracey et al., 2003).

1.4.5.2 FJX1 and 11p13 Chromosome Amplification in Human Cancers

Human FJX1 is located in the 11p13 chromosomal region. Even though there has been no previous studies pointing to a structural aberration of the region in NPC, it was found to be amplified across many types of primary tumors, including the breasts (Klingbeil et al., 2010), lungs (Lockwood et al., 2008; Sung et al., 2010; Starczynowski et al., 2011), gastric (Carvalho et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2011), oral (Snijders et al., 2005), esophageous (Miller et al., 2006; Chattopadhyay et al., 2010), prostate (Ma et al., 2009), small bowel (Diosdado et al., 2010) and acute myeloid myeloma (Sarova et al., 2010). In oral squamous cell carcinoma, FJX1 is both overexpressed and amplified in oral squamous cell carcinoma (Snijders et al., 2005).

Furthermore, other reports have shown that 11p13 is a frequent amplicon in cell lines derived from oral (Jarvinen et al., 2008), breast (Forozan et al., 1999), lung (Lockwood et al.,

2008; Sung et al., 2010; Starczynowski et al., 2011), and gastric (Fukuda et al., 2000) cancers. In addition, 11p13 is found to be significantly amplified in a huge study involving cancer cell lines of various origins (Beroukhim et al., 2010). In basal-like breast cancer, a neighboring gene CD44, was previously shown not to be the amplicon driver (Klingbeil et al., 2010), while TRAF6 was demonstrated to be one of the amplicon target in non-small-cell lung cancer (Starczynowski et al., 2011). Together, the results of these studies suggest that the amplification of 11p13 region might be important to the development of cancer in general, and FJX1 could be one of the amplicon targets.

1.5 HYPOTHESIS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Cancer Research Initiatives Foundation (CARIF) has conducted an expression microarray study to analyze genes that are differentially expressed in NPC relative to nonmalignant nasopharyngeal epithelial tissues from Malaysian subjects (Bose et al., 2009). With the previous identification of differentially upregulated genes in NPC from the study as the starting point, the hypothesis of this study is that genes that are significantly upregulated in NPC samples studied could be driver oncogenes in, or could serve as biomarkers for the disease.

The purpose of this study is to understand the molecular basis of NPC with an aim to develop biomarker(s) or therapeutic target(s) for NPC. The specific objectives were:

- 1. To identify genes that were up-regulated in NPC, but expressed minimally in normal human organs using expression microarrays**
- 2. To validate the microarray data by examining mRNA expression of the candidate genes in NPC tissue samples and normal human organs by quantitative- and semi-quantitative PCR, respectively.**

- 3. To examine the protein expression of the candidate genes in primary NPC tissue samples by immunohistochemistry, and to correlate the protein expression with clinicopathological features**
- 4. To determine the *in vitro* significance on alteration of the level of the candidate gene, which is FJX1, to the oncogenic traits of NPC cells**

CHAPTER II

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 CLINICAL COHORT AND SPECIMENS

All 27 NPC and 3 non-NPC cDNAs subjected for real-time quantitative PCR (Section 2.4.3) were derived from samples obtained from the Tung Shin Hospital, Kuala Lumpur. For immunohistochemistry (Section 2.5.4), 43 NPC and 11 non-NPC paraffin-embedded tissues were obtained from the Tung Shin Hospital, Kuala Lumpur and NCI Hospital, Negeri Sembilan. Prior informed consent was obtained from patients. The histologic characteristics of the non-NPC biopsies used in immunohistochemistry are summarized in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Non-NPC samples used in immunohistochemistry

Code	Histology
NPC 12	Nasopolyps (noncancerous growth of the nasal linings)
NPC 16	Nasopharyngitis (inflammation of the nasopharynx)
NPC 21	Normal epithelium
NPC 48	Synovial sarcoma (a form of soft tissue cancer)
NPC 51	Nasopharyngitis
NPC 65	Nasopharyngitis
NPC 73	Nasopharyngitis
NPC 84	Nasopharyngitis
NPC 88	Adenoid (mass of lymphoid tissue)
NPC 98	Nasopharyngitis
NPC 99	Lymphoid hyperplasia (enlarged lymph tissue), rhinosinusitis (inflammation of the nose tissue)

2.2 CELL LINES

NPC and immortalized nasopharyngeal epithelial cell lines used in this study, as well as their EBV status are summarized in Table 2.2. Cell lines were gifts from Professor SW Tsao (Department of Anatomy, University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China).

2.3 CELL CULTURE

2.3.1 Maintenance of cell lines

NPC cell lines CNE1, HONE1, HK1, SUNE1, TWO1, TWO4 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 (Gibco, Invitrogen, USA) containing 10% heat-inactivated FBS (Gibco, Invitrogen, USA). Immortalized nasopharyngeal epithelium NP69 cells were maintained in defined KSFM (Invitrogen, USA) supplemented with 5% FBS, 0.2µg/ml recombinant EGF (Invitrogen, USA), and 25µg/ml bovine pituitary extract (Invitrogen, USA). NP460 cells were cultured in 1:1 ratio of defined KSFM (Invitrogen, USA) and EpiLife (Invitrogen, USA). All cultures were maintained in a humidified chamber with 95% air and 5% CO₂ at 37°C and periodically checked for mycoplasma contamination (VenorGeM, Germany). Medium was changed thrice a week.

Table 2.2: Cell lines

Cell line	Origin	EBV status	Reference
CNE1	Differentiated NPC	Negative	("Establishment of an epitheloid cell line and a fusiform cell line from a patient with nasopharyngeal carcinoma," 1978)
HK1	Differentiated NPC, recurrent	Negative	(Huang et al., 1980)
HONE1	Undifferentiated NPC	Negative	(Glaser et al., 1989)
SUNE1	Undifferentiated NPC	Negative	(Chen et al., 1998)
TWO1	Differentiated NPC	Negative	(Lin et al., 1990)
TWO4	Undifferentiated NPC	Negative	(Lin et al., 1993)
NP460	Non-malignant nasopharyngeal epithelium, immortalized using hTERT	Negative	(Li et al., 2006)
NP69	Non-malignant nasopharyngeal epithelium, immortalized using SV40T	Negative	(Tsao et al., 2002)

2.3.2 Trypsinization of Cell Lines

Cells were passaged when they were about 70% in confluency. The culture medium was aspirated and the cells were rinsed once with PBS. The cells were detached by incubating with Trypsin-EDTA (Gibco, Invitrogen, USA) for 5min. An equal volume of 10% RPMI media was added to neutralize the enzymatic action. The cell suspension was centrifuged at $300 \times g$ for 5min and resuspended in the growth media. Cell count was done using CASY[®] Model TT cell counter (Roche Innovatis AG, Germany).

2.3.3 Cryopreservation of Cell Lines

1x10⁶ cells were resuspended in 1ml 10% RPMI containing 10% v/v DMSO for all NPC cell lines, or in FBS containing 10% DMSO for normal immortalized cell lines. Gradual freezing of the cells were achieved by storing in MrFrosty™ Cryo 1°C Freezing Container (Nalgene®, USA) in -80°C overnight before storing in liquid nitrogen.

2.4 MOLECULAR BIOLOGY

2.4.1 Total RNA Isolation

Total RNA was extracted from cultured cells that are at about 70% in confluency using Nucleospin® RNA II (Macherey-Nagel, Germany) according to manufacturer's protocol. RNA concentration was measured using NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, Thermo Scientific, USA). 1µg RNA was electrophoresed on 1% agarose gel containing trace amount of 10mg/ml ethidium bromide. The gel was viewed under ultraviolet (UV) rays using ChemImager (AlphaInnotech, USA). Two distinct bands of 28S and 18S ribosomal RNAs in a ratio of 2:1 indicate intact RNA.

2.4.2 First-strand cDNA Synthesis

A 12µl reaction mixture containing 1µl 10mM dNTP Mix (Promega, USA), 1µl OligodT primers (Promega, USA), 1µg total RNA and RNase-free water was heated at 65°C for 5min. Subsequently, 4µl of 5X First-Strand Buffer plus 2µl of 0.1M DTT were added to the reaction mixture. After incubation for 2min at 42°C, 1µl of 200U SuperScript II reverse transcriptase was added. The reaction was continued for another 50min at 42°C before inactivation at 70°C for 15min. The reaction was performed in a 500µl microcentrifuge tube using GeneAmp PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA).

2.4.3 Real-time Quantitative PCR (qPCR)

Gene-specific primers were designed using Primer Express 2.0 software (Applied Biosystems, USA) and synthesized by Sigma-Proligo (Singapore). Specificity of the primer pairs to the target transcript was verified by aligning to their respective mRNA sequences using BLAST algorithm (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). Primer sequences are listed in Table 2.3.

qPCR was performed using ABI Prism[®] 7000 Sequence Detection System (Applied Biosystems, USA). The reaction mixture contained 100ng first-strand cDNA, 7.5µl water, 12.5µl SYBR[®] Green PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, USA) and 2µl each of 10µM forward and reverse gene-specific primers (Sigma-Proligo, Singapore). The thermal cycling conditions were as follows: 10min at 95°C, followed by 40 cycles of 15 sec at 95°C and 1min at 60°C. In parallel, GAPDH was also amplified to serve as an internal control. Experiments were performed in triplicate for each reaction. A dissociation protocol was performed to confirm the specific amplification of the PCR products. In addition, the PCR products were electrophoresed on 2% agarose gel. Relative expression RQ was determined as $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$, where $\Delta\Delta CT = \Delta CT (\text{sample}) - \Delta CT (\text{calibrator})$. ΔCT means $CT(\text{target gene}) - CT(\text{GAPDH})$, where CT is the threshold cycle value.

Table 2.3: Primers Used in PCR

Target	Forward and Reverse Primer	Product Size (bp)
GAPDH	GAAGGTGAAGGTCGGAGTC GAAGATGGTGATGGGATTTTC	226
FJX1	CCCGCAAAGGTGTCTAAAAACT GTGCTGGCACAGTAAAGAATCCT	162
WNT5A	CATTATGGGCTCAAATAGAAAGAAGA AAAGAGCTAGGGTAGGCAACTAAAACT	124
CLCA2	TTCCACCTCCTCCCACATTC GGGCTCTGATCTCTCCTTTGC	201
CLDN1	CCGTTGGCATGAAGTGTATG CCAGTGAAGAGAGCCTGACC	208
FGFR3	GAATTCAGTTGTTCTGTTCTGTACTG AAAGTTCGTCGCTGGGTAAACA	172
FZD6	TGGCCTGAGGAGCTTGAATG GAGGCGCACACTGGTCAATT	202
RALA	TGCGGAATTCAAGTTACCAAT GGGTAGTGGCATCAGCCTAAGA	201
CD200	CCTGGTAATTCTTCTCGTCCTAATCT CTTTCGCTCCCACCTCTTTTG	200
CCND1	CCCTGACGGCCGAGAAG GGTCTGCGCGTGTTTGC	200
CCNE1	CTGGATGTTGACTGCCTTGAATT GCGACGCCCTGAAGTG	200

2.4.4 Semi-quantitative PCR (semi-qPCR)

Semi-qPCR was performed using GeneAmp PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA) in a 50 μ l reaction: 33.75 μ l water, 5 μ l 10x PCR Buffer II, 3 μ l 25mM MgCl₂, 1 μ l 10mM dNTPs, 1 μ l each of 10 μ M forward and reverse gene-specific primers, 0.25 μ l AmpliTaq Gold and 5 μ l of Human MTC™ Panel I or II (Clontech, USA) as the cDNA template. The reaction condition was as follows: 5min of 94°C, followed by 25, 30 or 35 cycles of 30sec each at 94°C, 59°C and 72°C, and finally 7min at 72°C. 5 μ l aliquots of the PCR products were visualized in 2% agarose gel.

2.4.5 Cloning of FJX1

The coding region of FJX1 was amplified from genomic DNA of NP460 cells using GC-RICH PCR System (Roche, Germany). The primers used were forward 5'-*CCCGGATCCACCATGGGCAGGAGGATG*-3' and reverse 5'-*GGAATTCCGAGTCCCAGACCGGCGGCCGTA*-3' (italics signifies *Bam*HI and *Eco*RI restriction sites in forward and reverse primers). The PCR product was electrophoresed on an agarose gel and a band at 1.3kb was excised from the agarose gel and purified using QIAQuick Gel Extraction Kit (Qiagen, the Netherlands). The purified PCR product was ligated into a cloning vector pGEM-T Easy (Promega, USA) in a 10 μ l ligation reaction: 5 μ l of 2X Rapid Ligation Buffer, 1 μ l (50ng) pGEM-T Easy Vector, 1 μ l of T4 DNA Ligase and 3 μ l of the PCR product. The ligation mixture was incubated overnight at 4°C prior to transformation into TOP10 competent *E.coli* cells. The competent cell/DNA mixture was incubated on ice for 20min, heat-shocked at 42°C for 30sec, and promptly placed on ice for 2min. 950 μ l of LB broth was added and the cells were shaken at 150 rpm, 37°C for 2hrs. 100 μ l of the transformation mix was spread on LB agar plate containing 100 μ g/ml ampicillin

(Sigma-Aldrich, USA) plus 0.5mM IPTG and 80µg/ml X-Gal. The plate was incubated overnight at 37°C. A single white colony bearing the plasmid with the gene insert was inoculated into 8mL of LB broth containing 100µg/mL ampicillin and cultured at 150 rpm, 37°C overnight. The plasmid was purified using MiniPrep Plasmid Extraction Kit (Qiagen, the Netherlands) following manufacturer's recommendation and sent for sequencing (FirstBase, Malaysia).

The FJX1 coding region was subsequently subcloned into a mammalian expression vector pcDNA3.1-V5/His-B (Invitrogen, USA) to generate a recombinant FJX1 protein tagged with V5 epitope at the C-terminal. 2µg of pcDNA3.1-V5/His-B plasmid or the purified pGEM-T Easy vector carrying FJX1 gene was digested using BamH1 and EcoR1 restriction enzymes: 3µl of 10X buffer, 0.3µl acetylated BSA, 0.75µl each of BamH1 and EcoR1 restriction enzymes in a 30µl reaction. The reaction was performed at 37°C for 3hr, before inactivation at 65°C for 15min. The digested DNA was separated in agarose gel and the DNA band of the correct molecular weight was excised from the agarose gel. The DNA content from the agarose was purified using QIAQuick Gel Extraction Kit (Qiagen, the Netherlands). The ligation reaction was carried out in a reaction containing 1µl T4 DNA Ligase (New England Biolabs, USA), 2µl 10X Buffer, 2µl pcDNA vector, and 15µl FJX1 DNA fragment. The reaction was performed for 10min at room temperature prior to transformation into competent *E.coli* cells as previously described.

A bacteria clone carrying the correct sequence was identified and the plasmid was purified using MaxiPrep Plasmid Extraction Kit (Qiagen, the Netherlands) following manufacturer's recommendation.

2.5 BIOCHEMISTRY

2.5.1 Protein Extraction

Cells at about 80% in confluency were washed twice with ice-cold PBS and incubated on ice for 20min in 1 or 2mL RIPA buffer [50mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 0.25% Na-deoxycholate, 1mM EDTA, 1% Halt-protease cocktail inhibitor (Roche, Germany), and 1mM Na₃VO₄]. The lysate was collected using a cell scraper and cleared via centrifugation at *10,000 x g* for 30min at 4°C. The supernatant was transferred to a new tube and stored in -80°C. An aliquot of the supernatant was used for protein concentration determination (Section 2.5.2).

2.5.2 Protein Concentration Determination

Protein concentration was determined using Coomassie Plus reagent (Pierce, Thermo Scientific). 300µl of Coomassie Plus reagent was incubated with 10µl of protein samples in a 96-well plate for 15min at room temperature. Absorbance at 595nm was measured in MultiSkan FC microplate reader (ThermoFischer Scientific, USA). The experiment was done triplicate per sample, and 10µl RIPA buffer plus 300µl Coomassie Plus was used as a blank reading. A standard curve was made using BSA solution in the range of 0 to 2,000µg/ml.

2.5.3 Western Blot

40µg protein samples were mixed with 6x sample buffer (6% SDS, 30% glycerin, 320mM Tris-HCl pH 6.8, 3% β-mercaptoethanol and trace bromophenol blue) and boiled for 5min at 95°C. The samples were then electrophoresed in SDS-PAGE, together with 4µl Precision Plus Protein™ Standards (Bio-Rad, USA).

The separated proteins were transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane with 0.45 μ m pore size (Thermo Scientific, USA) using a Mini Trans-Blot Electrophoretic Transfer Cell System (Bio-Rad, USA). The membrane was then blocked in blocking solution [5% non-fat skim milk in PBS] for 1hr before incubating with primary antibodies diluted in blocking solution for overnight at 4°C. The membrane was washed three times for 5min each with PBST [0.1% Tween-20 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in PBS]. The membrane was subsequently incubated with secondary antibodies diluted in blocking solution for 1hr at room temperature. After further washes with PBST (3x5min), the membrane was scanned using Odyssey Infrared Imaging System (Licor, USA). To reuse the blot with different primary antibodies, the affinity-bound antibodies were removed by incubating the membrane in 0.2M NaOH solution for 5min, followed by two washes in PBST. The membrane was subsequently blocked with the blocking solution, incubated with primary and secondary antibodies as described above. The antibodies and the concentration used are listed in Table 2.4.

2.5.4 Immunohistochemistry

Immunohistochemistry was performed using Dako REAL™ EnVision Detection System (DakoCytomation, Denmark). 5 μ m sections of formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissues were deparaffinized in 2 xylene soaks for 5min each and rehydrated through a series of graded ethanol (2 times in 100%, 2 times in 95%, and once in 70% ethanol) for 3min each. The tissue sections were treated with Antigen Retrieval Solution High pH (Link Technology, USA) pH 6.0 for 10 minutes in a microwave for antigen retrieval. After cooling to room temperature and two PBS washes for 5min each, sections were incubated in Dako REAL™ Peroxidase-Blocking Solution for 15min. The sections were subsequently rinsed twice with PBS and incubated with anti-human FJX1 Rabbit Polyclonal antibody (#ARP47013, Aviva

Systems Biology, USA) at 1:500 dilution in PBS. After 1hr incubation, the sections were rinsed with PBS and incubated with Dako REAL™ Envision™/HRP, Rabbit/Mouse (ENV) peroxidase-conjugated polymer for 30min. After further washes in PBS, the sections were developed using diaminobenzidine (DAB) chromogen and the reaction was stopped by subjecting the slides in running water. The sections were counterstained with Harris' haematoxylin (BDH Laboratories, USA), followed by water rinse, dehydration in graded alcohols, cleared in xylene and mounted in DPX (Fluka Biochemika, Switzerland).

2.5.5 Immunocytochemistry

Immunostaining of cultured cells was performed using Dako REAL™ EnVision Detection System (DakoCytomation, Denmark). 5hr after transfection, cells were trypsinized from a 6-well plate and seeded on a sterile glass slide placed in a 100mm² culture dish. The cells were allowed to adhere to the glass slide for at least two hours before adding 10ml RPMI media into the culture dish. After incubation overnight at 37°C, the glass slide was rinsed twice with PBS and fixed in acetone for 10min. After two washes in PBS, primary antibodies diluted in PBS were applied for 30min at room temperature. The slides were later rinsed with PBST 0.1% and incubated with labeled polymer conjugate for 30min at room temperature. Subsequently, the slides were rinsed with PBST 0.1%. The slides were developed in DAB chromogen for 10min and washed with water. Counterstaining for nuclei was done using Harris' haematoxylin (BDH Laboratories, USA). For mounting steps, the slides were initially immersed twice in ethanol for 2min each, following a single immersion in xylene for 3min. Mounting on a coverslip was done using DPX (Fluka Biochemika, USA). Antibodies and their concentrations are listed in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Antibodies Used in Western Blotting and Immunohistochemistry

Antibody	Concentration in Western	Concentration in immunohistochemistry
Mouse anti-Cyclin D1 (M7155, DakoCytomation, Denmark)	1:50	<i>Not done</i>
Mouse anti-Cytokeratin 5 (NCL-L-CK5, Leica Microsystems, Germany)	1:200	1:50
Mouse anti-Cytokeratin 10 (M7002, DakoCytomation, Denmark)	<i>Not suitable for Western</i>	1:50
Mouse anti-Vimentin (M0725, DakoCytomation, Denmark)	1:100	1:25
Mouse anti- β -Catenin (M35339, DakoCytomation, Denmark)	1:200	1:25
Rabbit anti-Twist (sc-15393, Santa Cruz, USA)	1:200	<i>Not done</i>
Rabbit anti-Snail (ab85931, Abcam, USA)	1:1,000	<i>Not done</i>
Rabbit anti-ZO1 (ab59720, Abcam, USA)	1:200	<i>Not done</i>
Rabbit anti-E-cadherin (abEP700Y, Abcam, USA)	1:2,000	1:50
Mouse anti-alpha tubulin (#T5168, Sigma, USA)	1:2,000	<i>Not applicable</i>
Rabbit anti-V5 (#ab9116, Abcam, USA)	1:2,000	1:500

Table 2.4, continued

Antibody	Concentration in Western	Concentration in immunohistochemistry
Goat anti-Mouse IRDye® 680 (#926-32220, Odyssey®, USA)	1:5,000	<i>Not applicable</i>
Goat anti-Rabbit IRDye® 800 (#926-32211, Odyssey®, USA)	1:5,000	<i>Not applicable</i>

2.6 *IN VITRO* ASSAYS

2.6.1 Transient Overexpression of Recombinant FJX:V5 Protein

2.5x10⁴ SUNE1 or 3.5x10⁴ TWO4 cells per well were seeded in 6-well plates and cultured overnight to reach 80-90% confluency. 250µl serum free media were mixed with 4µg plasmid DNA in an Eppendorf tube. In another tube 250µl serum free media was mixed with 16µg Lipofectamine™ 2000 Transfection Reagent (Invitrogen, USA). The contents of the two tubes were incubated separately for 5min and then combined. After incubation for another 20min, the transfection mixture was added to the cells in each well containing 2mL complete RPMI.

2.6.2 Transient Knockdown of Endogenous FJX1 Transcript

7.5x10⁴ HK1 cells were seeded in a well of 6-well plates to achieve 80-90% confluency after overnight incubation. The cells were transfected with either ON-TARGETplus SMARTpool siRNA against FJX1 or ON-TARGETplus Non-Targeting Pool siRNA (Dharmacon, Thermo Scientific, USA). Briefly, 200µl serum free media containing 5µl of 20µM siRNA and another 200µl serum free media containing 5µl DharmaFECT 1 were incubated separately in Eppendorf tubes for 5min. Subsequently, the contents from the tubes were combined and incubated for another 20min. This 400µl transfection mix was later added to the cells in a single well of 6-well plate containing 1.6mL complete RPMI. Sequences of the FJX1-targeting siRNA oligonucleotide species in the pool are: 5'-CGGAGCAGAUUCAGGGCGA-3', 5'-AGUACAAUGGACCGACUUA-3', 5'-UCGACUACCUGACGGCCA-3', and 5'-GGACUUAGUGUCACCGGGA-3'.

2.6.3 Proliferation Assay

24hr post-transfection with plasmid construct or siRNA, 50,000 TWO4 or HK1 cells per well were seeded into 6-well plates. Cells in triplicate wells were trypsinized using Trypsin-EDTA and counted using CASY[®] cell counter every day. The media was changed on day 3.

The mean cell counts and standard errors were calculated and two tailed Student's *t*-test was used to determine the statistical significance of the differences. $P < 0.05$ was taken as being statistically significant.

2.6.4 Transwell Migration Assay

Cell migration assay were performed using transwell inserts (8 μ m pore size; BD Biosciences, USA) in 24 Well MultiWell[™] Plate (BD Biosciences, USA). 1 day post-transfection with either plasmid or siRNA, the cells were treated with 15 μ l/mL mitomycin C for 2hr to limit their proliferative potential. The mitomycin C-treated cells were washed twice with migration buffer (0.1% BSA in serum-free RPMI), and 50,000 cells in 100 μ l of migration buffer were seeded into the inserts. The inserts were placed into the wells that contain 450 μ l migration buffer plus 50 μ l FBS. The plate was incubated in tissue culture incubator to allow cells to migrate. After 24hr, 500 μ l trypsin-EDTA was used to detach the migrated cells from the bottom of the membrane for at least 20min, and the total migrated cells were counted using the CASY[®] cell counter. The experiments were done in triplicates.

The mean migrated cell counts and standard errors were calculated and two tailed Student's *t*-test was used to determine the statistical significance. $P < 0.05$ was taken as being statistically significant.

2.6.5 Transwell Invasion Assay

Cell invasion assay were performed using transwell inserts (8µm pore size; BD Biosciences, USA) in 24 Well MultiWell™ Plate (BD Biosciences, USA). 1 day post-transfection with either plasmid or siRNAs, the cells were treated with 15µl/mL mitomycin C for two hours to limit their proliferative potential. The inside of transwell inserts was coated with 70µl of 2:1 mix of serum-free RPMI and Matrigel (BD Biosciences, USA) for one hour. The mitomycin C-treated cells were washed twice with migration buffer (0.1% BSA in serum-free RPMI), and 50,000 cells in 200µl migration buffer were seeded on top of the matrigel layer in the insert. 500µl 10% RPMI was placed in the wells and the plate was incubated in the tissue culture incubator. After 48hr, 500µl trypsin-EDTA was used to detach the cells from the bottom of the insert and the total invaded cells were counted using CASY® cell counter. The experiments were done in triplicates.

The mean invaded cell counts and standard errors were calculated and two tailed Student's *t*-test was used to determine the statistical significance of the differences in cell numbers between two different treatments. $P < 0.05$ was taken as being statistically significant.

2.6.6 Soft-agar Assay

Low-melting agarose VII (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in a Schott bottle was sterilized using UV rays. Complete RPMI was added to make a 1% agarose solution, and this solution was microwaved at low power. To prepare the 1% bottom agar layer, 2mL of the 1% agarose/RPMI was placed in a well of 6-well plates and left for at least 1 hour to solidify. The 0.5% top agar layer was prepared by mixing equal volumes of a suspension of 2,000cells/mL in complete RPMI and the 1% agarose/RPMI solution. 2mL of the cell/agarose solution was quickly dispensed on top of the bottom layer and, left for another hour to solidify, before

being put in the 37°C incubator. For assays using 12-well plates, 1,000 cells in 1ml top agar were added to 1ml of the bottom agar. Total number of colonies was counted under the microscope after 3 weeks.

The mean colony counts and standard errors were calculated and two tailed Student's *t*-test was used to determine the statistical significance of the differences in cell numbers between two different treatments. $P < 0.05$ was taken as being statistically significant.

CHAPTER III

RESULTS

3.1 CANDIDATE GENE SELECTION

A combination of microarray analysis and candidate-gene approach was employed to identify candidate biomarkers or oncogenes in NPC. First, overexpressed genes in NPC were identified from a previously published expression microarray study that compared 25 primary NPC against 3 non-malignant nasopharyngeal tissues (Bose et al., 2009). Subsequent overlapping of this gene list with genes that are expressed at low level in normal essential organs (microarray data set from bone marrow, brain, lung, liver, heart; Prof Yusuke Nakamura from Human Genome Centre, University of Tokyo, Japan), uncovered high priority candidate genes. 41 genes were identified to be upregulated in NPC but expressed at low level in important normal human organs.

For the purpose of developing monoclonal antibody therapies and serum biomarkers, 18 genes that encode for secreted or membrane-bound proteins were selected. Among these genes, seven of them were chosen on the basis of their involvement in aspects of normal development or in cancer pathophysiology as reported in literature from the period of December 2006 until February 2007. They are: 1) FJX1 (Ashery-Padan et al., 1999; Rock et al., 2005a; Rock et al., 2005b; Snijders et al., 2005; Yamaguchi et al., 2006; Jarvinen et al., 2008), 2) WNT5A (Rodolfo et al., 2004; Blanc et al., 2005a; Blanc et al., 2005b; Katoh et al., 2005; Turashvili et al., 2006), 3) CLCA2 (Gruber & Pauli, 1999; Abdel-Ghany et al., 2001; Bustin et al., 2001; Elble & Pauli et al., 2001; Konopitzky et al., 2002), 4) FZD6 (Katoh, 2005, 2007), 5) FGFR3 (Mhawech-Fauceglia et al., 2006; Schulz et al., 2006; Luis et al., 2007), 6) CLDN1 (Swisshelm et al., 2005; Kominsky, 2006), and 7) RALA (Ehrhardt et al., 2002; Oxford & Theodorescu, 2003; Camonis & White, 2005)

3.2 VALIDATION OF GENE EXPRESSION

3.2.1 Overexpression in primary NPC tissue samples

qPCR was performed to validate the overexpression of the 7 candidate genes in primary NPC tissues. Except RALA, all other 6 genes showed overexpression in virtually all of the NPC samples analyzed when compared to two biopsies of normal nasopharynx (NPC3 and TSE5) and a biopsy of nasopharyngitis (TSE16) that were used as controls. For each gene, the control sample with the highest level of expression was used as the calibrator (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 | Validation of upregulated expression of candidate genes in primary NPC tissues. (A to F) The overexpression of 6 out of the initial 7 candidate genes which was observed in microarray (Bose et al., 2009) were validated using qPCR. Compared to non-malignant controls (TSE5, NPC3, TSE16), the upregulation of these 6 candidate genes (FJX1, WNT5A, CLCA2, FZD6, FGFR3, and CLDN1) were shown in nearly all of the primary NPC tissue samples examined. (G) RALA, while was observed to be upregulated in the microarray data, failed validation. For each candidate gene, the control sample with the highest level of expression was used as the calibrator. Error bars delineate log RQ Min and Max.

3.2.2 Low expression in normal human organs

To validate the low expression of the 6 candidate genes in human organs, the expression of these genes was determined in a panel of 16 normal human organs using commercially available cDNAs, Human Multiple Tissue Panel™ (MTC) I and II, via semi-qPCR. The cDNA amount for each sample was normalized by the manufacturer (Clontech), obviating the need for loading control reactions.

When semi-qPCR was first performed using Panel I cDNAs which consists of cDNAs from heart, brain, placenta, lung, liver, skeletal muscle, kidney and pancreas, the expression of FJX1, WNT5A, and CLCA2 was shown to be generally low in the initial 8 organs examined (Figure 3.2A). These 3 genes were chosen for further validation in Panel II which consists of cDNAs from spleen, thymus, prostate, testis, ovary, small intestine, colon and peripheral blood leukocyte. Similarly, the expression of the 3 candidate genes was negligible in these 8 organs (Figure 3.2B), confirming the low expression of these genes in a wide range of normal human organs.

Figure 3.2 | Validation of low expression of candidate genes in normal human organs. Semi-qPCR for 35 cycles waperformed using commercial cDNAs derived from normal human organs (Human MTC™ Panel I and II) as templates. Experiment were done first using Human MTC™ Panel I, where FJX1, CLCA2 and WNT5A were deemed to be expressed at low level across the initial 8 normal human organs tested (A). Further semi-qPCR experiment using Human MTC™ Panel II showed that FJX1, CLCA2 and WNT5A were expressed at low level in another 8 normal human organs (B). “S.muscle” denotes smooth muscle (A), “PBL” denotes peripheral blood leukocyte (B), while “+” denotes positive control cDNA from NPC cell lines.

3.3 PROTEIN EXPRESSION IN PRIMARY NPC TISSUES

To determine whether the protein levels of FJX1, WNT5A and CLCA2 were overexpressed in primary NPC tissues, their protein expression and cellular location were examined in 43 samples of formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) primary NPC and 11 samples of non-malignant nasopharyngeal tissues by immunohistochemistry. The assessment of the staining was performed by a consultant pathologist, Prof Rajadurai Pathmanathan, from Sime Darby Medical Centre Subang Jaya, Subang Jaya.

While all 11 non-malignant nasopharyngeal tissues consistently showed no staining (Figure 3.3), FJX1 expression was significantly higher in 42% (18 out of 43) NPC tissues examined ($P=0.010$, Fisher's exact test). The staining was cytoplasmic, ranged in score from +1 to +3, and varied in pattern from focal to diffuse. Ductal structures in the tissue samples were always positive, demonstrating the specificity of the antibody (Figures 3.3C, 3.3E and 3.3G). However, no correlation was found between patient TNM status and FJX1 staining (Table 3.1).

Due to the insensitivity and unspecificity of the antibodies against WNT5A and CLCA2, the staining of these two candidate proteins on NPC tissues could not be completed. This study hereafter focused on FJX1 as the candidate biomarker/oncogene.

Figure 3.3 | FJX1 was upregulated at the protein level in NPC. Non-malignant nasopharyngeal tissues consistently stained negative for FJX1 (A). (B), a no-primary antibody negative control. (C), a representative NPC tissue void of FJX1 stain in malignant cells, but with staining in endothelial structure. Representative 2+ stain (D and E) and 3+ stain (F) are shown. (G) and (H) are close-up images of (C) and (F), respectively.

Table 3.1 | FJX1 immunohistochemistry analysis. FJX1 was overexpressed at protein level in NPC samples (18/43=42% NPC, all 11 non-NPC negative, $P=0.010$) as determined by immunohistochemistry. However, no correlation between patient TNM status with FJX1 immunohistochemistry stain was observed. P values were derived from Fisher's exact tests.

<u>Parameter</u>		<u>FJX1 staining status</u>			
		n	+	-	% +
Disease					
	non-NPC	11	0	11	0
	NPC	43	18	25	42
$P = 0.010$					
Tumor size					
	T1	6	3	3	50
	T2	19	8	11	42
	T3	12	4	8	33
	T4	6	3	3	50
$P = 0.948$					
Lymph node metastasis					
	N0	12	5	7	42
	N1	6	4	2	67
	N2	23	9	14	39
	N3	2	0	2	0
$P = 0.841$					
Stage					
	I	3	2	1	67
	II	7	4	3	57
	III	24	9	15	38
	IV	9	3	6	33
$P = 0.840$					

3.4 FJX1 expression in NPC and immortalized nasopharyngeal epithelium cell lines

In order to select cell lines that could be used for FJX1 *in vitro* studies, endogenous FJX1 transcript level was determined in a series of NPC and two immortalized nasopharyngeal epithelium cell lines (NP69 and NP460) by qPCR. Due to a lack of reliable commercial antibody against FJX1 for use in Western blotting, the level of endogenous FJX1 protein in the cell lines could not be determined. As determined by qPCR, the NPC cell lines expressed FJX1 at varied levels (Figure 3.4); when nonmalignant epithelial cell line NP69 was used as calibrator, HONE1 and HK1 cells expressed high amount of FJX1 transcript, whereas SUNE1 and TWO4 expressed FJX1 transcript at low level. Interestingly, another nonmalignant cell line NP460 expressed high level of FJX1 mRNA.

Figure 3.4 | FJX1 expression in NPC cell lines varies. qPCR on NPC and immortalized normal nasopharyngeal epithelium cell lines showed that FJX1 was expressed at varied levels. Calibration was made against immortalized nasopharyngeal epithelium cell line NP69. HK1 was chosen for loss-of-function while SUNE1 and TWO4 were chosen for gain-of-function studies. Error bars delineate log RQ Min and Max for each sample.

3.5 FJX1 *IN VITRO* STUDIES

3.5.1 Endogenous FJX1 knockdown

Depletion of endogenous FJX1 transcript was carried out using pooled small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) that consisted of siRNAs with four different sequences that target the coding region of FJX1 transcript (the FJX1-targeting siRNAs hereafter designated as siFJX) (Figure 2.1). Pooled siRNAs that bear no significant homology to any known human gene sequence was used as negative control (the control ‘non-targeting’ siRNAs hereafter is referred as siNT). Initially, HK1 and HONE1 cells which expressed high FJX1 transcript levels were chosen for knockdown purpose.

To establish an optimal condition for knockdown experiments, titration experiments were first performed to assess the siRNA concentration that would give the highest knockdown using 10, 30, 50 or 100nM of siRNA after 2 days. Time-course experiments were subsequently conducted to monitor the knockdown effect for a five day period. As previously mentioned (Section 3.4), the lack of a reliable commercial antibody did not permit the examination of FJX1 protein level on siRNA treatment. qPCR analysis was used instead to determine the level of FJX1 transcript.

3.5.1.1 FJX1 knockdown in HONE1 cells

For reasons unknown, two attempts of titration experiments using HONE1 cells failed to determine a consistent optimal siFJX concentration for FJX1 knockdown. Furthermore, a time-course experiment using 50nM siRNA showed that the inhibition of FJX1 transcript could only be sustained up to 2 days post-transfection (data not shown). Therefore, HONE1 cells were not used for any subsequent FJX1 knockdown assays.

3.5.1.2 FJX1 knockdown in HK1 cells

Among the four different siFJX concentrations tested, HK1 cells consistently exhibited the highest FJX1 knockdown when treated with 50nM siFJX (Figure 3.5A), with the inhibitory effect sustained up to 5 days (Figure 3.5B). The knockdown appeared to be FJX1-specific as no noticeable effect on FJX1 level between mock untreated and siNT-treated cells, as well as on the endogenous control gene GAPDH level between mock untreated, siNT- and siFJX-treated, was observed (data not shown). All ensuing loss-of-function *in vitro* assays employed only HK1 cells. Hereafter, HK-siNT is used to denote HK1 cells transfected with siNT, while HK-siFJX designates HK1 cells transfected with siFJX.

Figure 3.5 | Endogenous FJX1 knockdown in HK1 cells. siFJX titration experiments, performed twice, showed that optimal FJX1 knockdown after 2 days was achieved using 50nM siFJX. (A), Representative FJX1 expression on siFJX titration. Time-course FJX1 expression showed that knockdown of FJX1 was sustained until day 4 post-transfection (B).

3.5.2 Recombinant FJX1 protein overexpression

To perform gain-of-function studies, FJX1 coding region was cloned into pcDNA3.1-V5/His-B, a mammalian expression plasmid. The introduction of this construct in mammalian cells would result in a high expression of recombinant FJX1 protein with a C-terminal tag encoding the V5 epitope followed by a polyhistidine sequence (the recombinant protein hereafter designated as FJX:V5) (Figure 2.2). The expression of the FJX:V5 protein was detected using anti-V5 antibody in Western blotting and immunocytochemistry. Two NPC cell lines, TW04 and SUNE1 that expressed low level of endogenous FJX1 transcript were chosen for overexpression purpose.

To determine the expression of FJX1 protein, Western blot analysis was performed on pcDNA3.1-FJX1 transfected (designated TW04-FJX and SUNE-FJX) and vector control transfected (designated TW04-pcDNA and SUNE-pcDNA) cells. The recombinant FJX1 protein was not detected in TW04-pcDNA and SUNE-pcDNA, while TW04-FJX and SUNE-FJX showed a high level of recombinant FJX:V5 protein with a molecular mass close to the predicted size of 48kDa. Time course experiment showed that the transient FJX:V5 overexpression was sustained up until fourth day post-transfection (Figure 3.6). The expression of FJX1 protein was further confirmed in SUNE1- and TW04-FJX1 transfectants by immunocytochemistry. While vector-transfected cells were void of signal, intense brown staining was observed in SUNE- and TW04-FJX cells at the perinuclear area (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.6 | Overexpression of FJX:V5 in SUNE1 and TWO4 cells as detected by Western. Transient overexpression of recombinant FJX:V5 protein was sustained in SUNE1 (A) and TWO4 (B) cells until 4 days post-transfection. Asterisk (*) denotes sample lysate from TWO4-FJX:V5 day 1 that was used as positive control in the same blot for TWO4-pcDNA samples (B).

Figure 3.7 | Overexpression of FJX:V5 in SUNE1 and TWO4 cells as detected by immunocytochemistry. SUNE1 and TWO4 cells transfected with pcDNA3.1-FJX produced recombinant FJX1:V5 protein that was localized around the perinuclear area as revealed by immunocytochemistry using V5 antibody (brown stain, right panels). Cells transfected with vector plasmid meanwhile were void of the signal (left panels). The nucleus was stained blue with haematoxylin. All images were taken at the same magnification.

3.5.3 FJX1 promoted cell proliferation

To determine the contribution of FJX1 in cell growth, proliferation assay was done on HK1 and TWO4 cells following FJX1 knockdown and overexpression, respectively. Endogenous FJX1 depletion in HK1 cells impaired (Figure 3.8A), while enforced FJX:V5 expression in TWO4 enhanced cell proliferation (Figure 3.8B).

Figure 3.8 | FJX1 enhanced cell proliferation. Knockdown of endogenous FJX1 in HK1 cells decreased (A), while overexpression of FJX1 in TWO4 cells increased (B) cell proliferation as monitored over 5 days period. * $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.001$ (P -value of unpaired two tailed t -test).

3.5.3.1 FJX1 enhanced cell proliferation possibly through regulation of Cyclins

D1 and E1

To unravel the mechanism by which FJX1 affects proliferation, the transcript levels of cyclins D1 and E1 were determined in cells following overexpression and knockdown of FJX1. Knockdown of FJX1 in HK1 cells and overexpression of FJX:V5 in TWO4 respectively resulted in decrease (Figure 3.9A) and increase (Figure 3.9B) of cyclins D1 and E1 transcript levels.

Figure 3.9 | Alteration in FJX1 level was accompanied by change in cyclins D1 and E1 transcript. Knockdown of FJX1 in HK1 cells decreased (A), while overexpression of FJX1 increased transcript level of cyclins D1 and E1 (B).

3.5.4 Mitomycin C arrested cell proliferation without altering the effects of FJX1 knockdown or overexpression

To ensure the results of migration and invasion assays were not swayed by alteration of cell proliferation on FJX1 knockdown or overexpression, cells were treated with Mitomycin C, which inhibits cell mitosis via interfering with thymidine incorporation into DNA during replication (Schwartz et al., 1963), prior to the assays. Herein after, “mito C” suffix denotes cells with prior Mitomycin C treatment.

To assess whether the drug treatment would affect FJX1 expression following knockdown or overexpression, the FJX1 level was measured in the siRNA- or plasmid-transfected cells after mitomycin C treatment. The drug treatment did not alter the effectiveness of FJX1 knockdown or overexpression in HK1 or TW04 cells respectively, as well as did not cause any discernible change in proliferation (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10 | Mitomycin C treatment did not affect FJX1 knockdown or overexpression, but was effective in restricting cell proliferation. The knockdown effect of siFJX on endogenous FJX1 transcript in HK1 cells (A), and the overexpression of FJX:V5 in TWO4 cells (B), were not compromised by mitomycin C treatment. In both cases, the number of cells after a 2-day-period was not statistically different.

3.5.4.1 FJX1 did not change cell migratory ability towards FBS

To assess whether FJX1 is involved in cell migration, transwell migration assay was performed using HK1 and TWO4 cells following knockdown or overexpression of FJX1, respectively. When FBS was used as chemoattractant, neither knockdown nor overexpression of FJX1 resulted in a change of the migratory ability of the cells (Figure 3.11).

Figure 3.11 | FJX1 did not change migratory ability of cells towards FBS. Neither overexpression (A) nor knockdown (B) of FJX1 caused statistically significant change in the number of cells migrated towards FBS.

3.5.4.2 FJX1 enhanced cell invasion

To investigate the effect of FJX1 on the cell invasive ability, Matrigel invasion assay was performed using HK1 and TWO4 cells following overexpression and knockdown of FJX1, respectively. While knockdown of FJX1 caused reduced invasive ability of HK1 cells (Figure 3.12A), overexpression of FJX1 resulted in increased invasive ability of TWO4 cells (Figure 3.12B).

Figure 3.12 | FJX1 enhanced cell invasion. FJX1 knockdown decreased (A) while FJX1 overexpression increased (B) number of invaded cells through Matrigel, as measured by invasion assay. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ (P -value of unpaired two tailed t -test).

3.5.5 FJX1 increased anchorage-independent cell growth

Colony-formation assay was performed to assess the contribution of FJX1 in anchorage-independent cell growth. HK1 cells could not form colonies in soft agar despite several attempts, confirming previous observation (Wong et al., 2010). Hence, the assays were only done in a gain-of-function manner using TWO4 and SUNE1 cells. Overexpression of FJX1 in both TWO4 and SUNE1 cells resulted in an increased number of colonies in soft agar (Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13 | FJX1 facilitated anchorage-independent growth. TWO4 (A) and SUNE1 (B) cells transfected with FJX1 showed increased ability to form colonies in soft agar. Bars represent mean, while error bars represent standard deviation. * $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.001$ (P -value of unpaired two tailed t -test).

3.5.6 FJX1 was not involved in epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition and cellular differentiation

The enhancement of cell invasiveness by FJX1 might be explained in terms of change in epithelial or mesenchymal state of the cells, a developmental regulatory program known as Epithelial-to-Mesenchymal Transition (EMT). Therefore, the total levels of several EMT markers, as well as their cellular localization after knockdown or overexpression of FJX1 were determined using Western blotting and immunocytochemistry, respectively. No apparent change in total level (Figure 3.14) and localization (Figure 3.15) of the epithelial (β -catenin, E-cadherin, ZO-1) and mesenchymal (vimentin, snail, twist) markers was observed. For knockdown of FJX1 in HK1 cells, change in vimentin level could not be assessed as parental HK1 cells express undetectable level of vimentin.

In addition, to examine whether FJX1 is involved in cellular differentiation, the protein levels of keratinocyte differentiation markers CK5 and CK10 were determined. No obvious difference in the staining pattern or intensity between FJX1 cells and vector control cells was observed, demonstrating that FJX1 did not alter cellular differentiation *in vitro* (Figures 3.15 and 3.16).

Figure 3.14 | Change in FJX1 level was not accompanied with change in EMT and differentiation marker levels. Neither knockdown nor overexpression of FJX1 caused any significant change in level of epithelial (β -catenin, E-cadherin, ZO-1), mesenchymal (vimentin, snail, twist) or differentiation (CK5) markers. The change in vimentin level in HK1 cells could not be determined as the parental cells express very low vimentin.

Figure 3.15 | Change in FJX1 level was not accompanied with change in localization and staining intensity of EMT markers. Neither knockdown nor overexpression of FJX1 caused any significant change localization and staining intensity of epithelial (β -catenin, E-cadherin), mesenchymal (vimentin) and differentiation (CK5, CK10) markers. All images were taken at the same magnification. Scale bar in vimentin TWO4-pcDNA (top left) represents 100 μ m.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of the molecular pathogenesis of NPC has improved significantly over the years; however, the current understanding is still not sufficient to change the clinical practice in the management of NPC. Therefore, a better molecular understanding of the disease is needed, not just to identify which molecular pathways that are dysregulated, but also to have an in-depth understanding on their clinical values. For example, EGFR is overexpressed (Fang et al., 2007) and amplified (Hui et al., 2002) in NPC, but unlike in lung cancer, targeting the EGFR pathway has proved limited clinical significance in NPC (Elser et al., 2007; Ma et al., 2008).

The starting point of this study was to identify genes that are overexpressed in NPC while having negligible expression in normal human organs using microarrays. Seven candidate genes, FJX1, CLCA2, WNT5A, RALA, FZD6, CLDN1 and FGFR3 were initially identified as they code for secreted or membrane-bound proteins, as well as having prior association with neoplasia or normal development. Only FJX1 was found to be expressed at negligible level across normal human organs examined, as well as overexpressed at the protein level in primary NPC tissues. Therefore, FJX1 was chosen for future studies. The effects of elevated FJX1 expression in NPC were subsequently investigated *in vitro*. FJX1 was found to enhance cell proliferation, invasion, and colony-formation in soft agar, indicating a potential role of FJX1 as an oncogene in NPC.

4.1 CANDIDATE GENE SELECTION

The current mainstay methods of treatment for NPC, which are radiotherapy and chemotherapy, have been unable to improve the outlook of the disease due to severe undesirable complications. Targeted therapy, which includes small molecule inhibitors, monoclonal antibodies and cancer vaccination, is a new treatment method which functions by interfering with specific molecules involved in tumor growth and maintenance. A route for developing this type of therapy is prior identification of the target molecule preceding the development of the inhibiting agent.

During validation of expression of the initial seven candidate genes, RALA failed validation for its overexpression in primary NPC tissues (Section 3.2.1). Three other genes FZD6, CLDN1 and FGFR3 failed validation in normal human organs (Section 3.2.2) as they showed broad and significant expression across the organs examined, suggesting their involvement in normal physiological processes in the organs. Targeting these molecules could result in adverse events in patients. As an example, CLDN1 is a well-known component in epithelial tight junction that regulates paracellular permeability in many tissues, as well as is a component in keratinization process (Angelow et al., 2008; Morita et al., 2011). While therapy against CLDN1 has not been developed for any cancer so far, previous experience in targeting the angiogenic VEGF pathway has shown that disruption of this pathway causes impairment of important physiological systems, including cardiovascular and renal systems, with associated serious and potentially fatal consequences (Chen & Cleck, 2009). In addition, the immunohistochemical staining of CLCA2 and WNT5A could not be completed due to the insensitivity and unspecificity of the antibodies.

This study has focused on the human FJX1, the homolog of *Drosophila fj* which is predicted to be a type II transmembrane protein (Villano & Katz, 1995). Like Fj and murine FJX1, human FJX1 protein might also be secreted and function at the extracellular (Probst et al., 2007; Rock et al., 2005; Villano & Katz, 1995). In addition, Fj is a Golgi kinase that phosphorylates specific extracellular cadherin domains of two gigantic transmembrane molecules, Fat and Dachous (Ishikawa et al., 2008). If FJX1 mainly exerts its function at the extracellular, the development of monoclonal antibody against the protein could be viable. Meanwhile, the amino acid residues crucial for the kinase activity is conserved in human FJX1, suggesting a possibility to develop FJX1-specific small molecule inhibitors.

4.2 FJX1 EXPRESSION IN NPC AND NORMAL ORGANS

During the course of the present study, a meta-analysis (Lan et al., 2010) comparing three independent expression microarray datasets (Fang et al., 2008; Shi et al., 2006; Sriuranpong et al., 2004) also identified FJX1 to be overexpressed in NPC compared to normal controls. Several lines of evidence indicate FJX1 might be involved in carcinogenesis. Endothelial cells isolated from ovarian cancers showed increased FJX1 expression compared to those from healthy ovaries (Buckanovich et al., 2007; Lu et al., 2007). FJX1 was also amplified and overexpressed in oral squamous cell carcinoma (Jarvinen et al., 2008; Snijders et al., 2005). In addition, FJX1 expression is associated with kidney metastasis of non-small cell lung cancer cells in mice (Kakiuchi et al., 2003). However, the protein expression and functional role of FJX1 in NPC has not been studied.

After validation of FJX1 overexpression at the transcript level via qPCR in primary NPC tissues (Section 3.2.1), immunohistochemistry was employed to determine FJX1 protein expression in paraffin-embedded primary NPC tissues (Section 3.3). FJX1 protein was overexpressed in a subset of NPC cases, which however lacked any correlation with clinicopathologic parameters (T category, N category and overall staging). This might be due to the small sample size in certain categories that was unable to offer a statistically significant inference.

In general, FJX1 transcript was detected at low levels in 16 of the normal human organs tested (Figure 3.2). The expression of FJX1 in some of these organs is comparable as previously seen in mouse (Ashery-Padan et al., 1999; Rock et al., 2005). In particular, Rock *et al.* reported that mouse FJX1 expression in the kidneys was lower than in the brain (Rock et al., 2005), an observation that was similar in this study. The low expression of FJX1 in normal organs implies that systemic introduction of FJX1-targeted therapy is likely to result in minimal adverse effect.

4.3 KNOCKDOWN AND OVEREXPRESSION OF FJX1

The effect of introducing FJX1-targeting siRNAs could only be measured at the transcript level via qPCR as there was no reliable antibody that could detect endogenous FJX1 protein. Although the antibody used in the immunohistochemical analysis was specific against FJX1 protein in paraffin-embedded tissue samples, it was not suitable in Western blotting. This might be due to FJX1 protein being easily and irreversibly denatured by the SDS treatment in Western blotting procedure, resulting in loss of epitope conformation that might be required for recognition by the antibody. An attempt to generate a custom-made antibody against an-FJX1

derived peptide was made during the course of this study; however, the antibody also failed to detect FJX1 protein in Western blotting.

Analysis of FJX1 overexpression using V5 antibody revealed the occasional detection of three different molecular weight of FJX1 protein in Western blotting (Figure 3.6A). This could be as a result of differential glycosylation of the recombinant protein. There are two potential *N*-linked glycosylation sites on human FJX1 protein sequence which are also conserved in mouse (Figure 1.3) (Rock et al., 2005). The potential existence of an unglycosylated form of FJX1, plus two other different forms with glycosylation at a single or both sites, could explain the occurrence of the three bands. However, to resolve whether this is a natural occurrence or merely an artifact of overexpression awaits the development of a reliable antibody to detect endogenous FJX1.

The recombinant FJX:V5 protein was localized at the perinuclear area of the cells (Figure 3.7), an observation that agrees with previous reports showing *Drosophila* Fj is located at the Golgi compartment both *in vivo* and *in vitro* (Ishikawa et al., 2008; Strutt et al., 2004). Double staining of FJX1 with specific intracellular vesicle or compartment marker is warranted to confirm its Golgi localization.

4.4 IN VITRO STUDIES OF FJX1

Both knockdown and overexpression experiments showed that FJX1 promoted aggressiveness of NPC cells by enhancing cell proliferation, anchorage-dependent growth and cellular invasion. The oncogenic traits tested are important in determining FJX1 oncogenicity in NPC: sustained proliferation and active tissue invasion have been proposed as cancer hallmark

capabilities (Hanahan & Weinberg, 2011), while anchorage-independent growth in soft agar is considered to be a stringent measurement of oncogenic properties as it is a close approximation to tumorigenicity assays in mouse (Chin & Gray, 2008).

Given that *Drosophila fj* and murine FJX1 are known to be downstream targets of the Notch signaling pathway (Buckles et al., 2001; Rock et al., 2005; Zeidler et al., 1999), it is possible that FJX1 is also a direct target of the pathway in NPC. The Notch signaling pathway, conserved across the metazoans, regulates many fundamental biological processes in a variety of tissues. The dysregulation of this pathway has been frequently reported in human cancers (Kopan & Ilagan, 2009), including NPC (Zhang et al., 2010). In particular, Notch can drive tumorigenesis through the promotion of cell cycle progression by inducing Cyclin D1 and Myc (Ranganathan et al., 2011). Furthermore, the inhibition of the Notch pathway in an NPC cell line CNE1 has been shown to inhibit proliferation and promote apoptosis, accompanied by downregulation of cyclins D and E1 (Chen et al., 2011). In this study, concomitant change of the levels of cyclin D1 and E1 is observed with FJX1 expression level, suggesting that FJX1 might promote proliferation through the Notch signaling.

The dysregulation of the Hippo tumor suppressor pathway is another potential mechanism through which FJX1 acts to modulate cell proliferation. The Hippo pathway regulates animal organ size by controlling cell proliferation and cell death (Dong et al., 2007), and its dysregulation has been increasingly implicated in human cancers (Zhao et al., 2010). The *Drosophila Fj* modulates the interaction of Fat and Dachshous, the upstream signalling regulators of Hippo pathway, through its kinase activity (Brittle et al., 2010; Ishikawa et al., 2008; Simon et al., 2010). This pathway has been shown to control cell proliferation by regulating Cyclin E in

Drosophila (Bennett & Harvey, 2006; Harvey et al., 2003; Silva et al., 2006; Udan et al., 2003; Willecke et al., 2006). In the present study, the level of Cyclin E1 positively correlated with FJX1 expression in NPC cells (Section 3.5.3.1), implicating FJX1 could be a downstream target of Hippo pathway in human. Currently the only knowledge on the Hippo pathway in NPC is that an important regulator LATS2 was reported to be overexpressed in NPC with its expression correlates with poor prognosis (Zhang et al., 2010).

Cyclins D1 and E1 are responsible in mediating G1-S phase progression of the cell cycle. However, cell cycle analysis using Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting (FACS) in the FJX1-knockdown or -overexpressing cells yielded inconsistent results (data not shown). Therefore, additional experiments to determine the role of FJX1 in regulating cell cycle progression in NPC cells are required.

One of the cellular responses to oncogenic transformation is structural rearrangement of the actin cytoskeleton, leading to the formation of specialized structures involved in cell locomotion (Hall, 2009; Nurnberg et al., 2011). To determine whether FJX1 influences the migration of NPC cells, experiments were undertaken to examine the effect of FJX1 knockdown and overexpression using transwell assays. FJX1 did not cause any change in cell migration when FBS was used as a chemoattractant (Figure 3.11). Other chemoattractants such as fibronectin and vitronectin were however not included in this study. In addition, the use of transwells to examine cell migration does not faithfully recapitulate *in vivo* situation as they lack the complex interplay between tumor and the stromal environment that is vital for cell migration. Therefore, the role of FJX1 in regulating cellular migration remains inconclusive.

FJX1 enhanced invasive ability of the NPC cells through Matrigel (Section 3.5.4.2), a gelatinous protein mixture derived from culture secreted by Engelbreth-Holm-Swarm (EHS) mouse sarcoma that is known to resemble extracellular environment in many tissues (Benton et al., 2011). The re-initiation of the developmental regulatory program EMT during tumorigenesis could enable epithelial tumor cells to acquire invasive capability (Kalluri & Weinberg, 2009). However, no alteration in the expression of EMT-associated markers was seen in both knockdown and overexpression experiments (Section 3.5.6). Previously, tumor cells have been found to be able to remodel the actin cytoskeleton via podoplanin, a small mucin-like protein, to acquire invasive phenotype that is independent of EMT. Podoplanin induces actin remodeling to promote filopodia formation, important cellular structure for invasion, via downregulation of small Rho family GTPases (Wicki & Christofori, 2007; Wicki et al., 2006). The acquisition of more invasive phenotype via podoplanin-mediated pathway might offer an explanation on the lack of correlation of invasion with EMT seen in this study.

While de-regulation of the Notch or Hippo pathways might contribute to the up-regulation of FJX1 in NPC, other possible mechanisms also exist, including chromosomal amplification and EBV infection. FJX1 is located at 11p13, a region that has been repeatedly shown to be amplified in many types of human primary cancer tissues and cell lines, including cancers of the breasts (Klingbeil et al., 2010), gastric (Carvalho et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2011), oral (Snijders et al., 2005), lung (Lockwood et al., 2008; Starczynowski et al., 2011; Sung et al., 2010), esophageous (Chattopadhyay et al., 2010; Miller et al., 2006), prostate (Ma et al., 2009), small bowel (Diosdado et al., 2010) and acute myeloid myeloma (Sarova et al., 2010). In addition, 11p13 is found to be significantly amplified in cancer cell lines derived from various

different origins (Beroukhim et al., 2010). EBV is the viral etiological agent in NPC and it is well recognized that EBV alters many functional properties that are involved in tumor progression (Raab-Traub, 2002). It is a possibility EBV infection could contribute to the overexpression of FJX1 in NPC. Therefore, additional studies investigating the mechanisms that are responsible for overexpression of FJX1 in NPC are warranted.

CONCLUSION

FJX1 is a candidate oncogene in NPC. It is overexpressed at both the transcript and protein levels in NPC, as well as expressed at low level in human organs. It promotes proliferation, invasion and anchorage-independent growth in NPC cells. Furthermore, its expression is accompanied by concomitant change in Cyclins D1 and E1, without change in neither EMT nor differentiation status. In summary, FJX1 represent an attractive therapeutic target for NPC.

In the future, it is necessary to establish the genetic circumstance of FJX1 overexpression in NPC, not only to ascertain the mechanism of FJX1 overexpression, but also to shed light onto the pathways to which it belongs. Furthermore, as FJX1 is also amplified in other cancers as well as potentially has kinase activity, the protein might also be a candidate oncogene in other human neoplasia. *In vitro* assays on knocking down of FJX1 in FJX1-amplified cancer cell lines would verify whether the gene is a driver of the 11p13 amplicon that is observed in various cancers. To conclusively implicate FJX1 as a candidate oncogene in NPC as well as other cancers, *in vivo* tumorigenicity assay would be required. Finally, the identification of an FJX1-specific inhibitor might pave the way for an FJX1-based therapeutic intervention in NPC and potentially other cancers.

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